

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOMAIN INTRODUCTION

Information security is the process of securing information data from unauthorized access, use, modification, tampering, or disclosure. With the increased use of electronics media in our personal lives as well as businesses, the possibility of security breach and its major impact has increased. The theft of personal identity, credit card information, and other important data using hacked user names and passwords have become common these days. In addition, the theft of confidential business data may lead to loss of business for commercial organizations.

A vulnerability is a weakness in design, implementation, operation or internal control. Most of the vulnerabilities that have been discovered are documented in the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) database.

1.1.1 TYPES OF INFORMATION SECURITY

BACKDOOR

A backdoor in a computer system, a cryptosystem or an algorithm, is any secret method of bypassing normal authentication or security controls. They may exist for a number of reasons, including by original design or from poor configuration. They may have been added by an authorized party to allow some legitimate access, or by an attacker for malicious reasons; but regardless of the motives for their existence, they create a vulnerability.

DENIAL-OF-SERVICE ATTACKS

Denial of service attacks (DoS) are designed to make a machine or network resource unavailable to its intended users. Attackers can deny service to individual victims, such as by deliberately entering a wrong password enough consecutive times to cause the victims account to be locked, or they may overload the capabilities of a machine or network and block all users at once.

1.2 PROBLEM DEFINITION

The word is used in information technology, including: network forensics the capture, recording, and analysis of network events in order to discover the source of security attacks or other problem incidents. The word forensics refers to used for formal public debate or discussion.

1.3 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Centre for education and research Information Assurance and Security (CERIAS) is a center for research and education in areas of information security that are crucial to the protection of critical computing and communication infrastructure. Key exposure is one serious security problem for cloud storage auditing.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

1. TITLE:Enabling Cloud Storage Auditing with Verifiable
Outsourcing of Key Updates

AUTHOR: Jia Yu, Kui Ren, Senior Member, IEEE, and Cong Wang, Member,
IEEE

YEAR: 2017

ABSTRACT:

Key-exposure resistance has always been an important issue for in-depth cyber defence in many security applications. It defines how to deal with the key exposure problem in the settings of cloud storage auditing has been proposed and studied. To address the challenge, existing solutions all require the client to update his secret keys in every time period, which may inevitably bring in new local burdens to the client, especially those with limited computation resources such as mobile phones. It focus on how to make the key updates as transparent as possible for the client and propose a new paradigm called cloud storage auditing with verifiable outsourcing of key updates. In this paradigm, key updates can be safely outsourced to some authorized party, and thus the key-update burden on the client will be kept minimal

2. TITLE:Public Integrity Auditing for Dynamic Data Sharing with Multi-User
Modification

AUTHOR: Jiawei Yuan, Shucheng Yu

YEAR: 2016

ABSTRACT

The rapid development of cloud storage services makes it easier than ever for cloud users to share data with each other. To ensure users' confidence of the integrity of their shared data on cloud, a number of techniques have been proposed for data integrity auditing with focuses on various practical features. Most of the techniques consider that only the original data owner can modify the shared data, which limits these techniques to client read-only applications. A few attempts started considering more realistic scenarios by allowing multiple cloud users to modify data with integrity assurance.

3. TITLE: Identity-Based Data Outsourcing with Comprehensive Auditing in
Clouds

AUTHOR: Yujue Wang, Qianhong Wu, Bo Qin, Wenchang Shi Robert H. Deng

YEAR: 2015

ABSTRACT:

Cloud storage system provides facilitative file storage and sharing services for distributed clients. To address integrity, controllable outsourcing and origin auditing concerns on outsourced files, it propose an identity-based data outsourcing (IBDO) scheme equipped with desirable features advantageous over existing proposals in securing outsourced data. First,IBDO scheme allows a user to authorize dedicated proxies to upload data to the cloud storage server on her behalf. The proxies are identified and authorized with their recognizable identities, which eliminates complicated certificate management in usual secure distributed computing systems. Second,IBDO scheme facilitates comprehensive auditing, i.e., our scheme not only permits regular integrity auditing as in existing schemes for securing outsourced data, but also allows to audit the information on data origin, type and consistence of outsourced files. Security analysis and experimental evaluation indicate that IBDO scheme provides strong security with desirable efficiency.

4. TITLE: Auditing Anti-Malware Tools by Evolving Android Malware and
Dynamic Loading Technique

AUTHOR: Yinxing Xue, Guozhu Meng, Yang Liu, Tian Huat Tan, Hongxu Chen,
Jun Sun, and Jie Zhang

YEAR: 2015

ABSTRACT:

Existing antimalware tools (AMTs) may have high detection rate. The report is based on existing malware and thus it does not imply that AMTs can effectively deal with future malware. It is desirable to have an alternative way of auditing AMTs. It use malware samples from android malware collection GENOME to summarize a malware meta-model for modularizing the common attack behaviors and evasion techniques in reusable features. It then combines different features with an evolutionary algorithm, in which way we evolve malware for variants. Previous results have shown that the existing AMTs only exhibit detection rate of 20%–30% for 10,000 evolved malware variants. In this paper, based on the modularized attack features, it apply the dynamic code generation and loading techniques to produce malware, so that we can audit the AMTs at runtime.

5. TITLE: Auditing a Cloud Provider's Compliance with Data Backup Requirements: A Game Theoretical Analysis

AUTHOR: Ziad Ismail, Christophe Kiennert, Jean Leneutre, and Lin

YEAR: 2014

ABSTRACT:

The new developments in cloud computing have introduced significant security challenges to guarantee the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of outsourced data. A Service Level Agreement (SLA) is usually signed between the cloud provider and the customer. For redundancy purposes, it is important to verify the cloud provider's compliance with data backup requirements in the SLA. There exists a number of security mechanisms to check the integrity and availability of outsourced data. This task can be performed by the customer or be delegated to an independent entity that we will refer to as the verifier. However, checking the availability of data introduces extra costs, which can discourage the customer of performing data verification too often.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

EXISTING SYSTEM

- More organizations and individuals would like to store their data in the cloud.
- The data stored in the cloud might be corrupted or lost due to the inevitable software bugs, hardware faults and human errors in the cloud.
- sensitive information should not be exposed to others when the cloud file is shared.
- Encrypting the whole shared file can realize the sensitive information hiding, but will make this shared file unable to be used by others.
- If the file has been hacked by hacker it only recovers the file.

DISADVANTAGE OF EXISTING SYSTEM

- The cloud and the shared users are untrustworthy, all of the sensitive information of the file will not be exposed to them.
- The explosive growth of data, it is a heavy burden for users to store the sheer amount of data locally.
- Remote data integrity auditing schemes cannot support data sharing with sensitive information hiding.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

- Remote data integrity auditing is future to guarantee the integrity of the data stored in the cloud.
- In some common cloud storage systems the cloud file strength contains some sensitive information.
- It explore how to achieve data sharing with sensitive information hiding in identity-based integrity auditing for secure cloud storage.
- A sanitizer is used to sanitize the data blocks corresponding to the sensitive information of the file and transforms these data blocks' signatures into valid ones for the sanitized file.
- These signatures are used to verify the integrity of the sanitized file in the phase of integrity auditing.
- As a result, scheme makes the file stored in the cloud able to be shared and used by others on the condition that the sensitive information is hidden, while the remote data integrity auditing is still able to be efficiently executed.

ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

- The sanitizer can be viewed as the administrator of the information system in a hospital. The personal sensitive information should not be exposed to the sanitizer.
- To preserve the privacy of patient from the sanitizer, the medical doctor will blind the patient's sensitive information of each record before sending this record to the sanitizer.
- The medical doctor then generates signatures for this blinded record and sends them to the sanitizer. The sanitizer stores these messages into record information system.

3.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

The feasibility of the project is analyzed in this phase and business proposal is put forth with a very general plan for the project and some cost estimates. During system analysis the feasibility study of the proposed system is to be carried out. This is to ensure that the proposed system is not a burden to the company. For feasibility analysis, some understanding of the major requirements for the system is essential. The key considerations are:

- **ECONOMICAL FEASIBILITY**
- **TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY**
- **SOCIAL FEASIBILITY**

3.3.1 ECONOMICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the economic impact that the system will have on the organization. The amount of fund that the company can pour into the research and development of the system is limited. The expenditures must be justified. Thus the developed system as well within the budget and this was achieved because most of the technologies used are freely available.

3.3.2 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the technical feasibility. Any system developed must not have a high demand on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands being placed on the client. The developed system must have a modest requirement, as only minimal or null changes are required for implementing this system.

3.3.3 SOCIAL FEASIBILITY

The aspect of study is to check the level of acceptance of the system by the user. This includes the process of training the user to use the system efficiently. The user must not feel threatened by the system, instead must accept it as a necessity. The level of acceptance by the users solely depends on the methods that are employed to educate the user about the system and to make him familiar with it.

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Design Engineering deals with the various diagrams for the implementation of project. Design is the creation of a plan or convention for the construction of an object, system or measurable human interaction such as in architectural blueprints, engineering drawings, business process, circuit diagrams and sewing patterns. Design has different connotations in different fields. Software design is a process through which the requirements are translated into representation of the model.

Fig.4.1 System Architecture

4.2 UML DIAGRAMS

4.2.1 USE CASE DIAGRAMS

A use case diagram is a type of behavioral diagram created from a Use-case analysis. The purpose of use case is to present overview of the functionality provided by the system in terms of actors, their goals and any dependencies between those use cases.

Fig.4.2 USE CASE DIAGRAMS

4.2.2 SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

A sequence diagram shows, as parallel vertical lines (“lifelines”), different processes or objects that live simultaneously, and as the horizontal arrows, the messages exchanged between them, in the order in which they occur. This allows the specification of simple run time scenarios in a graphical manner.

Fig.4.3 SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

4.2.3 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM

Activity diagrams are graphical representations of workflows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency. In the Unified Modeling Language, activity diagrams can be used to describe the business and operational step-by-step workflow of components in a system. An activity diagram shows the overall flow of control.

Fig.4.4 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM

4.2.4 CLASS DIAGRAM

Class diagram is UML structure diagram which shows structure of the designed system at the level of classes and interfaces, shows their features constraints and relationships -associations, generalizations, dependencies, etc . A class diagram in the UML is a type of static structure diagram that describes the structure of a system by showing the system’s classes, their attributes, and the relationships between the classes

Fig 4.5 CLASS DIAGRAM

4.3 DATAFLOW DIAGRAM

LEVEL 1

LEVEL 2

LEVEL 3

LEVEL 4

Fig.4.6 DATAFLOW DIAGRAM

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

The most common set of requirements is defined by the any system or the software application is the physical computer resources, also known as hardware, a hardware requirements list is often accompanied by a Hardware Compatibility List (HCL), especially in case of operating system.

- Processor : I3,I5,I7
- Speed : 2.2 GHz
- RAM : 4 GB (min)
- Hard Disk : 250 GB

5.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

The software requirements deals with defining software resource requirements and prerequisites that needs to be installed on a computer to provide optimal functioning of an application.

- Operating system : Windows
- Technology Used : Asp.net C#
- IDE : MicroSoft Visual Studio
- Database : MicroSoft Sql Server

5.3 EXTERNAL INTERFACE REQUIREMENTS

PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENTS

The performance of this demo depends on executing this project on LAN or wifi communication channel. So we need to have one or more machine to execute the demo.

SAFETY REQUIREMENTS

The software may be safety-critical. If so, there are issues associated with its integrity level. The software may not be safety-critical although it forms part of a safety-critical system. If a system must be of a high integrity level and if the software is shown to be of that integrity level, then the hardware must be at least of the same integrity level. There is little point in producing 'perfect' code in some language if hardware and system software are not reliable. Systems with different requirements for safety levels must be separated. Otherwise, the highest level of integrity required must be applied to all systems in the same environment.

SECURITY REQUIREMENTS

The Software Quality Attributes are

- Functionality are the required functions available, including Interoperability and security.
- Reliability maturity, fault tolerance and recoverability
- Usability how easy it is to understand, learn, and operate the software System
- Efficiency performance and resource behavior.
- Maintainability Maintaining the software.

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

INTRODUCTION TO DOTNET

NET will allow the creation of truly distributed Web services that will integrate and collaborate with a range of complementary services to help customers in ways that today's dotcoms can only dream of. The fundamental idea behind .NET is that the focus is shifting from individual Web sites or devices connected to the Internet to constellations of computers, devices, and services that work together to deliver broader, richer solutions. People will have control over how, when, and what information is delivered to them. Computers, devices and services will be able to collaborate with each other to provide rich services, instead of being isolated islands where the user provides the only integration. Businesses will be able to offer their products and services in a way that lets customers seamlessly embed them in their own electronic fabric. Microsoft .NET will make computing and communicating simpler and easier than ever. It will spawn a new generation of Internet services, and enable tens of thousands of software developers to create revolutionary online services and businesses. It will put you back in control, and enable greater control of your privacy, digital identity, and data. And software is what makes it all possible. However, Microsoft's .NET technology will only succeed if others adopt this new standard.

WORKING OF DOTNET

When the interpreter executes a class, it looks for a particular method by the name of main, which will sound familiar to C programmers. The main method is passed as a parameter an array of strings and is declared as a static method.

.Net consists of two things :

- Programming language
- Platform

THE .NET PLATFORM

Language interoperability offers many benefits. In addition, the .NET Framework can package old and new components to work together. This allows companies to reuse the code. As a platform-independent environment, .net can be a bit slower than native code.

6.2 MICROSOFT VISUAL STUDIO

Microsoft Visual Studio is an integrated development environment (IDE) from Microsoft. It is used to develop computer programs for Microsoft Windows, as well as web sites, web apps, web services and mobile apps. Visual Studio uses Microsoft software development platforms such as Windows API, Windows Forms, Windows Presentation Foundation, Windows Store and Microsoft Silverlight. It can produce both native code and managed code.

Visual Studio includes a code editor supporting IntelliSense as well as code refactoring. The integrated debugger works both as a source-level debugger and a machine-level debugger. It accepts plug-ins that enhance the functionality at almost every level—including adding support for source control systems and adding new toolsets like editors and visual designers for domain-specific languages or toolsets for other aspects of the software development lifecycle.

MICROSOFT SQL SERVER

Microsoft SQL Server is a relational database management system developed by Microsoft. As a database server, it is a software product with the primary function of storing and retrieving data as requested by other software applications—which may run either on the same computer or on another computer across a network.

DATA STORAGE:

Data storage is a database, which is a collection of tables with typed columns. SQL Server supports different data types, including primary types such as Integer, Float, Decimal, Char, Varchar, binary, Text among others.

Microsoft SQL Server also allows user-defined composite types (UDTs) to be defined and used. It also makes server statistics available as virtual tables and views. A SQL Server database can contain a maximum of 2^{31} objects, and can span multiple OS-level files with a maximum file size of 2^{60} bytes (1 hexa byte). The data in the database are stored in primary data files. Secondary data files are used to allow the data of a single database to be spread across more than one file, and optionally across more than one file system.

BUFFER MANAGEMENT

SQL Server buffers pages in RAM to minimize disk I/O. Any 8 KB page can be buffered in-memory, and the set of all pages currently buffered is called the buffer cache. The amount of memory available to SQL Server decides how many pages will be cached in memory. The buffer cache is managed by the Buffer Manager. Either reading from or writing to any page copies it to the buffer cache. Subsequent reads or writes are redirected to the in-memory copy, rather than the on-disc version. The page is updated on the disc by the Buffer Manager only if the in-memory cache has not been referenced for some time. While writing pages back to disc, asynchronous I/O is used whereby the I/O operation is done in a background thread so that other operations do not have to wait for the I/O operation to complete. Each page is written along with its checksum when it is written. When reading the page back, its checksum is computed again and matched with the stored version to ensure the page has not been damaged or tampered with in the meantime.

CONCURRENCY AND LOCKING

SQL Server allows multiple clients to use the same database concurrently. As such, it needs to control concurrent access to shared data, to ensure data integrity—when multiple clients update the same data, or clients attempt to read data that is in the process of being changed by another client. SQL Server provides two modes of concurrency control: pessimistic and optimistic.

When pessimistic concurrency control is being used, SQL Server controls concurrent access by using locks. Locks can be either shared or exclusive. Exclusive lock grants the user exclusive access to the data—no other user can access the data as long as the lock is held. Shared locks are used when some data is being read—multiple users can read from data locked with a shared lock, but not acquire an exclusive lock.

SQL SERVER MANAGEMENT STUDIO

SQL Server Management Studio is a GUI tool included with SQL Server 2005 and later for configuring, managing, and administering all components within Microsoft SQL Server. The tool includes both script editors and graphical tools that work with objects and features of the server. SQL Server Management Studio replaces Enterprise Manager as the primary management interface for Microsoft SQL Server since SQL Server 2005. A version of SQL Server Management Studio is also available for SQL Server Express Edition, for which it is known as SQL Server Management Studio Express (SSMSE).

4.3 LIST OF MODULES

FILE UPLOADING AND ACTIVATION

The data owner firstly needs to generate signatures for data blocks before uploading them to the cloud. These signatures are used to prove the cloud truly possesses these data blocks in the phase of integrity auditing. The data owner uploads these data blocks along with their corresponding signatures to the cloud. The data stored in the cloud is often shared across multiple users in many cloud storage applications

DATA INTEGRITY AUDITING

Data integrity auditing scheme that realizes data sharing with sensitive information hiding. The data stored in the cloud might be corrupted or lost. Data integrity auditing on the condition that the sensitive information of shared data is protected.

SENSITIVE INFORMATION SHARING

Sensitive information hiding to ensure that the personal sensitive information of the file is not exposed to the hacker. All of the sensitive information of the file should not be exposed to the cloud and the shared users. This method not only realizes the remote data integrity auditing, but also supports the data sharing on the condition that sensitive information is protected in cloud storage.

GENERATING KEY SIGNATURE

A potential method of solving this problem is to encrypt the whole shared file before sending it to the cloud. It then generate the signatures used to verify the integrity of this encrypted file. Finally upload this encrypted file and its corresponding signatures to the cloud. This method can realize the sensitive information hiding since only the data owner can decrypt this file. It will make the whole shared file unable to be used by others.

FILE SECURITY AND RECOVERY

If a file has been partially overwritten or otherwise compromised, the chances of any usable recovery are low. In our proposed work, we can easily recover the file while deleted files are inaccessible.

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 CODING

Once the design aspect of the system is finalized, the system enters into coding and testing phase. The coding phase brings the actual system into action by converting the design of the system into code in a given programming language. Therefore, a good coding style has to be taken whenever changes are required, as it is easily screwed into the system.

7.2 CODING STANDARDS

Coding standards are guidelines to programming that focus on the physical structure and appearance of the program. They make the code easier to read, understand, and maintain. This phase of the system actually implements the blueprint developed during the design phase. The coding specification should be in such a way that any programmer must be able to understand the code and can bring about changes whenever felt necessary.

7.3 TEST PROCEDURE

7.3.1 SYSTEM TESTING

Testing is performed to identify errors. It is used for quality assurance. Testing is an integral part of the entire development and maintenance process. The goal of the testing during phase is to verify that the specification has been accurately and completely incorporated into the design, as well as to ensure the correctness of the design itself. For example, the design must not have any logic faults in the design.

detected before coding commences, otherwise the cost of fixing the faults will be considerably higher as reflected. Detection of design faults can be achieved by means of inspection as well as walkthrough.

7.3.2 UNIT TESTING

Unit testing is conducted to verify the functional performance of each modular component of the software. Unit testing focuses on the smallest unit of the software design (i.e.), the module. The white-box testing techniques were heavily employed for unit testing.

7.3.3 FUNCTIONAL TEST

Functional test cases involved exercising the code with nominal input values for which the expected results are known, as well as boundary values and special values, such as logically related inputs, files of identical elements, and empty files. Three types of tests in Functional test: performance test, stress test, functional test.

7.3.4 INTEGRATION TESTING

Integration testing is a systematic technique for construction the program structure while at the same time conducting tests to uncover errors associated with interfacing. The objective is to take untested modules and build a program structure tester should identify critical modules.

7.4 TEST CASE RESULT

Test	Requirements or Purpose	Test data	Expected result	Actual result	P/F
1	Data Owner Registration.	Username, password, email-id, captcha.	Getting registered into the server	Same as expected	Pass
2	Data user Login.	Username, password.	Getting logged into the server	Same as expected	Pass
3	File upload and file sending.	Select the file from cloud storage.	Upload the file and send to destination	Same as expected	Pass
4	File uploading is complete.	Server sleep mode is activate.	Server goes to sleep mode	Same as expected	Pass
5	Server sleep mode is activate.	Mail will be send in server admin.	Mail received server	Same as expected	Pass
6	Download the original file.	To click the download button.	Download the file from cloud server	Same as expected	Pass

Table 7.1 Test Case Result

CHAPTER 8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the existing system, the data stored in the cloud might be corrupted or lost due to the inevitable software bugs, hardware faults and human errors in the cloud. The sensitive information should not be exposed to others when the cloud file is shared. Encrypting the whole shared file can realize the sensitive information hiding, but will make this shared file unable to be used by others. If the file has been hacked by hacker it only recovers the file. In this paper, we propose how to achieve data sharing with sensitive information hiding in identity-based integrity auditing for secure cloud storage. The signatures are used to verify the integrity of the sanitized file in the phase of integrity auditing. As a result, our scheme makes the file stored in the cloud able to be shared and used by others on the condition that the sensitive information is hidden, while the remote data integrity auditing is still able to be efficiently executed.

In the proposed system if the file has been hacked by the hacker it not only recovers the file but it also recovers the content because the original file will be hidden behind the duplicate file.

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

9.1 CONCLUSION

A character based information respectability reviewing plan for secure distributed storage, which bolsters information offering to delicate data covering up. The record put away in the cloud can be shared and utilized by others depending on the prerequisite that the touchy data of the document is ensured. The remote information honesty examining is still ready to be proficiently executed. The security evidence and the exploratory investigation exhibit that the proposed plot accomplishes attractive security and productivity.

9.2 FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

The data owner independently upload the data to the Cloud and it is difficult to monitor the data and checking the process. This can be achieved by introducing Proxy component to check for the integrity. This is an added advantage to the data owner that he need not stay for integrity checking. The data owner provides a key to the proxy server using that key proxy is responsible for checking the data. This should be considering as the future work to overcome this drawback.

APPENDICES

A . SAMPLECODE

```
<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeFile="Home.aspx.cs"
Inherits="Home" %>
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="zxx">
<head>
<title>Auditing Data</title>
<!-- Meta tag Keywords -->
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta charset="UTF-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Cakes Bakery Responsive web template,
Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG,
SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script>
addEventListener("load", function () {
setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);
}, false);
function hideURLbar() {
window.scrollTo(0, 1);
}
</script>
<!-- //Meta tag Keywords -->
<!-- Custom-Files -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.css">
```

```

<!-- Bootstrap-Core-CSS -->
<link href="css/login_overlay.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/style.css" type="text/css" media="all" />
<!-- Style-CSS -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/fontawesome-all.css">
<!-- Font-Awesome-Icons-CSS -->
<!-- //Custom-Files -->
<!-- Web-Fonts -->
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Oxygen:300,400,700&subset=latin-
ext" rel="stylesheet">
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:300,300i,400,400i,600,600i,
700,700i,800,800i&subset=cyrillic,cyrillic-ext,greek,greek-ext,latin-
ext,vietnamese" rel="stylesheet">
<link href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Pacifico&subset=cyrillic,latin-
ext,vietnamese" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- //Web-Fonts -->
</head>
<body><div class="mian-content"><!-- header --><header>
<nav class="navbar navbar-expand-lg navbar-light"><div class="logo text-left">
<h1><a class="navbar-brand" href="">Auditing Data</a></h1></div>
<button class="navbar-toggler" type="button" data-toggle="collapse" data-
target="#navbarSupportedContent" aria-controls="navbarSupportedContent" aria-
expanded="false" aria-label="Toggle navigation">
<span class="navbar-toggler-icon"></span></button>
<div class="collapse navbar-collapse" id="navbarSupportedContent">

```

```

<button id="prev"><i class="fas fa-chevron-left"></i></button>
<!-- image container -->
<div id="slider"></div>
<!-- next button -->
<button id="next"><i class="fas fa-chevron-right"></i>
</button>
<!-- small circles container --><div id="circles"></div></div>
<!-- end of main image slider container --><!-- Modal -->
<!-- //Model --><!-- //banner --></div><!-- //main -->
<!-- banner-bottom -->
<!-- //banner-bottom-w3layouts --><!-- cake --><!-- //cake -->
<!-- services --><!-- //services -->
<!-- stats section --><!-- //stats section -->
<!-- copyright --><p class="copy-right-grids text-light my-lg-5 my-4 pb-4">©
Cloud Audit Data. All Rights Reserved </p>
<!-- //copyright --></div>
<!-- chef -->
<!-- //chef --></footer><!-- //footer -->
<!-- Js files --><!-- JavaScript -->
<script src="js/jquery-2.2.3.min.js"></script>
<!-- Default-JavaScript-File -->
<!Class('navicon--active');
$('.toggle').toggleClass('toggle--active');});
</script><!-- //menu-js --><!-- banner slider -->
<script src="js/image-slider.js"></script>
<link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="css/image-slider.css">
<!-- //banner slider --><!-- smooth scrolling -->

```

```
<script src="js/SmoothScroll.min.js"></script><!-- move-top -->
<script src="js/move-top.js"></script>
<!-- easing --><script src="js/easing.js"></script>
<!-- necessary snippets for few javascript files -->
<script src="js/cakes-bakery.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.js"></script>
<!-- Necessary-JavaScript-File-For-Bootstrap --><!-- //Js files --></body></html>
```

Register

```
<%@PageLanguage="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeFile="ClientRegister.aspx.cs" Inherits="ClientRegister" %>

<!DOCTYPE html>

<html lang="zxx"><head><title>Auditing Data</title><!-- Meta tag Keywords -->

<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta charset="UTF-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Cakes Bakery Services Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template, Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script>addEventListener("load", function () {
setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);}, false);
function hideURLbar() {
window.scrollTo(0, 1);}</script>
<!-- //Meta tag Keywords --><!-- Custom-Files -->
```

```

cmd = new SqlCommand("select * from ClientDetails where MobileNumber='" +
TextBox5.Text + "'", con1);
dr1 = cmd.ExecuteReader();
if (dr1.Read()){
Response.Write("<script>alert('MobileNo already Exist')</script>");}
else{
con2.Open();
cmd = new SqlCommand("select * from ClientDetails where MailID='" +
TextBox1.Text + "'", con2);
dr2 = cmd.ExecuteReader();
if (dr2.Read()){
Response.Write("<script>alert('MailId already Exist')</script>");}
else{
con3.Open();
cmd = new SqlCommand("insert into ClientDetails values('" + TextBox1.Text + "','" +
TextBox2.Text + "','" + TextBox4.Text + "','" + TextBox5.Text + "','" + date +
"', 'Waiting')", con3);
cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
con3.Close();
Response.Write("<script>alert('Submitted Successfully')</script>");}
con2.Close(); }
con1.Close();
con.Close();
clear();}}

```

Login

```

<%@PageLanguage="C#"AutoEventWireup="true"CodeFile="ClientLogin.aspx.c
s" Inherits="ClientLogin" %>

```

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="zxx">
<head>
<title>Auditing Data</title>
<!-- Meta tag Keywords -->
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta charset="UTF-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Cakes Bakery Services Responsive web
template, Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web
template, Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia,
Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script>
addEventListener("load", function () {
setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);}, false);
function hideURLbar() {
window.scrollTo(0, 1);}
</script>
<!-- //Meta tag Keywords --><!-- Custom-Files -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.css"><!-- Bootstrap-Core-CSS -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/style.css" type="text/css" media="all" />
<!-- Style-CSS --><link rel="stylesheet" href="css/fontawesome-all.css">
<!-- Font-Awesome-Icons-CSS --><!-- //Custom-Files --><!-- Web-Fonts --><link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Oxygen:300,400,700&subset=latin-
ext" rel="stylesheet">
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:300,300i,400,400i,600,600i,

```

```

<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="">Client</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">File Upload</li></ol>
</nav></div><!-- //page details --><!-- contact page -->
<div class="address py-5"><div class="container py-xl-5 py-lg-3">
<div align="center"><div ><div class="address-grid">
<h4 class="font-weight-bold mb-3">File Upload</h4>
<form action="#" method="post" runat="server"><table><tr>
<div class="form-group"><asp:TextBox ID="TextBox1" runat="server"
class="form-control" placeholder="" required="" Height="50" Width="400"
style="text-align: center" ForeColor="#0000CC" Font-Bold="True" Font-
Italic="True" ReadOnly="true"></asp:TextBox> </div></tr>
<tr><div class="form-group"><asp:TextBox ID="TextBox2" runat="server"
class="form-control" placeholder="" required="" Height="50" Width="400"
style="text-align: center" ForeColor="#0000CC" Font-Bold="True" Font-
Italic="True" ReadOnly="true"></asp:TextBox> </div></tr>
<tr><div class="form-group"><asp:TextBox ID="TextBox3" runat="server"
class="form-control" placeholder="File Name" required="" Height="50"
Width="400" style="text-align: center"></asp:TextBox></div></tr>
<tr><div class="form-group"><asp:FileUpload ID="FileUpload1" runat="server"
class="form-control" required="" Width="400" style="text-align: center"/></div>
</tr>
<tr><asp:Button ID="Button1" runat="server" Text="Submit" Height="50"
Width="400" OnClick="Button1_Click" /></tr> </table></form></div></div>
</div></div></div>
SqlDataReader dr;
SqlDataReader dr1;
SqlDataReader dr2;

```

```

DataSet ds = new DataSet();
SqlConnection con4 = new SqlConnection(ConfigurationManager.
ConnectionStrings["Audit"].ConnectionString.ToString());
SqlCommand cmd4;
private void EncryptFile(){
string input = Server.MapPath("~/Files/") + TextBox3.Text + ".txt";
string output = Server.MapPath("~/FilesE/") + TextBox3.Text + ".txt";
FileUpload1.SaveAs(input);
this.Encrypt(input, output);}
private void Encrypt(string inputFilePath, string outputFilePath){
string EncryptionKey = "MAKV2SPBNI99212";
using (Aes encryptor = Aes.Create()){
Rfc2898DeriveBytes pdb = new Rfc2898DeriveBytes(EncryptionKey, new byte[] {
0x49, 0x76, 0x61, 0x6e, 0x20, 0x4d, 0x65, 0x64, 0x76, 0x65, 0x64, 0x65, 0x76 });
encryptor.Key = pdb.GetBytes(32);
encryptor.IV = pdb.GetBytes(16);
using (FileStream fsOutput = new FileStream(outputFilePath, FileMode.Create)){
using(CryptoStreamcs= new CryptoStream(fsOutput, encryptor.CreateEncryptor(),
CryptoStreamMode.Write)){
using (FileStream fsInput = new FileStream(inputFilePath, FileMode.Open){
int data;
while ((data = fsInput.ReadByte()) != -1){
cs.WriteByte((byte)data);}}}}}}
private void fileupload(){
con2.Open();
cmd2 = new SqlCommand("select * from FileUpload where FileName="" +
TextBox3.Text + """, con2);

```

```

dr2 = cmd2.ExecuteReader();
if (dr2.Read()){
Response.Write("<script>alert('File Name Already Exist')</script>");}
else{
string fileExtension=Path.GetExtension(FileUpload1.PostedFile.FileName);
if (fileExtension == ".txt"){
using(BinaryReader br=new BinaryReader(FileUpload1. PostedFile,InputStream))
{byte[] bytes=br.ReadBytes(int)FileUpload1.PostedFile.InputStream.Length);
int siz = (int)FileUpload1.PostedFile.InputStream.Length;
string Size = siz.ToString() + "kb";
string contenttype = FileUpload1.PostedFile.ContentType;
string filename = FileUpload1.FileName;
String filename1 = TextBox3.Text;
string date = DateTime.Now.ToString("dd/MM/yyyy");
using (SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand()){
cmd.CommandText = "insert into FileUpload(ClientMailID, ClientName,
FileName, UploadFile, ContentType, Data, FileSize, Date, ClientStatus,
ProxyStatus, FileKey) values (@ClientMailID , @ClientName, @FileName,
@UploadFile, @ContentType, @Data, @Size, @date, @ClientStatus,
@ProxyStatus, @FileKey)";
cmd.Parameters.AddWithValue("@ClientMailID", TextBox1.Text);
cmd.Parameters.AddWithValue("@ClientName", TextBox2.Text);
cmd.Parameters.AddWithValue("@FileName", filename1);
cmd.Parameters.AddWithValue("@UploadFile",Path.GetFileName(FileUpload1.P
ostedFile.FileName));
cmd.Parameters.AddWithValue("@ContentType", "application/word");
cmd.Parameters.AddWithValue("@Data", bytes);

```

```

cmd.Parameters.AddWithValue("@Size", Size);
cmd.Parameters.AddWithValue("@Date", date);
cmd.Parameters.AddWithValue("@ClientStatus", "Waiting");
cmd.Parameters.AddWithValue("@ProxyStatus", "Waiting");
cmd.Parameters.AddWithValue("@FileKey", "Waiting");
cmd.Connection = con;
con.Open();
cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
con.Close();
EncryptFile();
con4.Open();
cmd4 = new SqlCommand("insert into AuditDetails
values('"+TextBox3.Text+"','FileUpload','"+TextBox2.Text+"','"+DateTime.Now.
ToString()+"'",con4);
cmd4.ExecuteNonQuery();
con4.Close();
Response.Write("<script>alert('File Upload Successfully')</script>");}}
else{Response.Write("<script>alert('Text File Only Upload')</script>");}}
con2.Close();}
private void ad(){
protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e){
fileupload();
TextBox3.Text = "";}}

```

Search Files

```

<%@PageLanguage="C#"AutoEventWireup="true"CodeFile="SearchFiles.aspx.cs
" Inherits="SearchFiles"%>
<!DOCTYPE html>

```

```

<html lang="zxx"><head><title>Auditing Data</title><!-- Meta tag Keywords -->
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta charset="UTF-8" /><meta name="keywords" content="Cakes Bakery
Services Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates,
Android Compatible web template, Smartphone Compatible web template, free
webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script>
addEventListener("load", function () {setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);}, false);
function hideURLbar() {
window.scrollTo(0, 1);}
</script><!-- //Meta tag Keywords --><!-- Custom-Files -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.css"><!-- Bootstrap-Core-CSS -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/style.css" type="text/css" media="all" />
<!-- Style-CSS --><link rel="stylesheet" href="css/fontawesome-all.css">
<!-- Font-Awesome-Icons-CSS --><!-- //Custom-Files --><!-- Web-Fonts -->
<linkhref="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Oxygen:300,400,700&subset=
latin-ext" rel="stylesheet">
<linkhref="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:300,300i,400,400i,600,
600i,700,700i,800,800i&subset=cyrillic,cyrillic-ext,greek,greek-ext,latin-
ext,vietnamese" rel="stylesheet">
<linkhref="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Pacifico&subset=cyrillic,latin-
ext,vietnamese" rel="stylesheet"><!-- //Web-Fonts --></head>
<body><div class="mian-content"><!-- header --><header>
<nav class="navbar navbar-expand-lg navbar-light"><div class="logo text-left">
<h1><a class="navbar-brand" href="">Auditing Data</a></h1></div>
<button class="navbar-toggler" type="button" data-toggle="collapse" data-

```

```

<a class="nav-link dropdown-toggle" href="#" id="navbarDropdown"
role="button" data-toggle="dropdown" aria-haspopup="true" aria-expanded="false">
END USER</a>
<div class="dropdown-menu text-left text-center" aria-labelledby="navbarDropdown"
<a class="dropdown-item" href="EndUserRegister.aspx" title="">REGISTER</a>
<a class="dropdown-item" href="EndUserLogin.aspx" title="">LOGIN</a>
</div></li></ul><!-- menu button --><div class="menu">
con4.Open();
cmd4 = new SqlCommand("insert into AuditDetails values('"+ DropDownList1.Text
+ "', 'File Hacked', 'Hacker', '" + DateTime.Now.ToString() + "')", con4);
cmd4.ExecuteNonQuery();
con4.Close(); con.Open(); cmd = new SqlCommand("insert into CheckData values('"
+ DropDownList1.Text + "')", con);
cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
con.Close(); } }

```

KGC Generate Key

```

<%@Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeFile="KGCGenerateKey.
aspx.cs" Inherits="KGCGenerateKey"%>
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="zxx"><head><title>Auditing Data</title><!-- Meta tag Keywords -->
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta charset="UTF-8" /><meta name="keywords" content="Cakes Bakery
Services Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web
<span class="sr-only">(current)</span></a></li><li class="nav-item active">
<a class="nav-link" href="KGCGenerateKey.aspx">GENERATE KEY</a></li>
<li class="nav-item"><a class="nav-link" href="KGCUserRequest.aspx">USER
REQUEST</a></li><li class="nav-item">

```

```

<a class="nav-link" href="Home.aspx">LOGOUT</a></li></ul>
<!-- menu button --><div class="menu"><a href="#" class="navicon"></a>
<div class="toggle"><ul class="toggle-menu list-unstyled"><li>
<a href="KGCTransaction.aspx">View_Transaction</a></li>
<li><a href="Home.aspx">Home</a></li></ul></div></div>
<!-- //menu button --></div></nav></header><!-- //header --><!-- banner 2 -->
<div class="banner2-w3ls"></div><!-- //banner 2 --></div><!-- main -->
<!-- page details --><div class="breadcrumb-agile">
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb"><ol class="breadcrumb m-0">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="">KGC</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Key Generate</li></ol>
</nav></div><!-- //page details --><!-- contact page -->
<div class="address py-5"><div class="container py-xl-5 py-lg-3">
<div align="center"><div ><div class="address-grid"><h4 class="font-weight-
bold mb-3">Key Generate</h4><form id="form1" runat="server"><table><tr>
<div class="form-group"><asp:GridView ID="GridView1" runat="server"
AutoGenerateColumns="False" BackColor="#DEBA84" BorderColor="#DEBA84"
BorderStyle="None" BorderWidth="1px" CellPadding="3" CellSpacing="2" Font-
Size="15pt" DataSourceID="SqlDataSource1" style="text-align: center">
<Columns>
<asp:BoundField DataField="FileName" HeaderText="FileName" SortExpression="
FileName" /><asp:BoundField DataField="UploadFile" HeaderText="Upload File"
SortExpression="UploadFile" /><asp:BoundField DataField="Date"
<p class="copy-right-grids text-light my-lg-5 my-4 pb-4">© Cloud Audit Data. All
Rights Reserved</p><!-- //copyright --></div>
<!-- chef -->
<!-- //chef --></footer><!-- //footer --><!-- Js files --><!-- JavaScript -->

```

```

string a = gvrow.Cells[0].Text;
// string date = DateTime.Now.ToString("dd/MM/yyyy");
con3.Open();cmd = new SqlCommand("update FileUpload set FileKey='"+ key + "'
where FileName='"+ a + "'", con3);
cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();con3.Close();
Response.Redirect("KGCGenerateKey.aspx");}}

```

File Details

```

<%@PageLanguage="C#"AutoEventWireup="true"CodeFile="ProxyFileUpload.a
spx.cs" Inherits="ProxyFileUpload"%>
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="zxx"><head><title>Auditing Data</title><!-- Meta tag Keywords -->
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta charset="UTF-8" /><meta name="keywords" content="Cakes Bakery
Services Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates,
Android Compatible web template, Smartphone Compatible web template, free
webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design"
/><script>
addEventListener("load", function () {setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);}, false);
function hideURLbar() {window.scrollTo(0, 1);}</script>
<!-- //Meta tag Keywords --><!-- Custom-Files -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.css"><!-- Bootstrap-Core-CSS -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/style.css" type="text/css" media="all" />
<!-- Style-CSS --><link rel="stylesheet" href="css/fontawesome-all.css">
<!-- Font-Awesome-Icons-CSS --><!-- //Custom-Files --><!-- Web-Fonts -->
<linkhref="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Oxygen:300,400,700&subset=
latin-ext" rel="stylesheet">

```

```

<linkhref="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:300,300i,400,400i,600,600i,700,700i,800,800i&subset=cyrillic,cyrillic-ext,greek,greek-ext,latin-ext,vietnamese" rel="stylesheet">
<linkhref="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Pacifico&subset=cyrillic,latin-ext,vietnamese" rel="stylesheet"><!-- //Web-Fonts --><style type="text/css">
.auto-style1 {width: 261px;}</style></head><body>
<div class="mian-content"><!-- header --><header>
<nav class="navbar navbar-expand-lg navbar-light"><div class="logo text-left">
<h1><a class="navbar-brand" href="">Auditing Data</a></h1></div>
<button class="navbar-toggler" type="button" data-toggle="collapse" data-target="#navbarSupportedContent"aria-controls="navbarSupportedContent" aria-expanded="false" aria-label="Toggle navigation">
<span class="navbar-toggler-icon"></span></button>
<div class="collapse navbar-collapse" id="navbarSupportedContent">
<ul class="navbar-nav ml-lg-auto text-lg-right text-center"><li class="nav-item ">
<a class="nav-link" href="ProxyHome.aspx">HOME
<span class="sr-only">(current)</span></a></li><li class="nav-item ">
<a class="nav-link" href="ProxyClientInformation.aspx">
CLIENTINFORAMATION</a></li> <li class="nav-item active">
<a class="nav-link" href="ProxyFileUpload.aspx">AUTHORIZE FILE
UPLOAD</a></li><li class="nav-item">
<a class="nav-link" href="Home.aspx">LOGOUT</a></li></ul>
<!-- menu button --><div class="menu"><a href="#" class="navicon"></a>
<div class="toggle"><ul class="toggle-menu list-unstyled"><li>
<a href="ProxyUserInformation.aspx">User_Information</a></li>
<li><a href="ProxyTransaction.aspx">View_Transaction</a></li>
<li><a href="Home.aspx">Home</a></li></ul></div></div>

```

```

SqlConnection con1 = new SqlConnection(ConfigurationManager.
ConnectionStrings["Audit"].ConnectionString.ToString());
SqlConnection con2 = new SqlConnection(ConfigurationManager.
ConnectionStrings["Audit"].ConnectionString.ToString());
SqlConnection con3 = new SqlConnection(ConfigurationManager.
ConnectionStrings["Audit"].ConnectionString.ToString());
SqlCommand cmd;SqlDataAdapter da;
DataTable dt = new DataTable();
SqlDataReader dr;
SqlDataReader dr1;
SqlDataReader dr2;
DataSet ds = new DataSet();
SqlConnection con4 = new SqlConnection(ConfigurationManager.
ConnectionStrings["Audit"].ConnectionString.ToString());SqlCommand cmd4;
protected void LinkButton1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e){
LinkButton lnkbtn = sender as LinkButton;
GridViewRow gvrow = lnkbtn.NamingContainer as GridViewRow;
string a = gvrow.Cells[1].Text;
// string date = DateTime.Now.ToString("dd/MM/yyyy");
con3.Open();
cmd = new SqlCommand("update FileUpload set ProxyStatus='Activated' where
FileName='" + a + "'", con3);cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();con3.Close();
Response.Write("<script>alert('Activated Successfully')</script>");
Response.Redirect("ProxyFileUpload.aspx");
Response.Write("<script>alert('Activated Successfully')</script>");}
protected void LinkButton2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e){
LinkButton lnkbtn = sender as LinkButton;

```

```

GridViewRow gvrow = lnkbtn.NamingContainer as GridViewRow;
string a = gvrow.Cells[1].Text;
// string date = DateTime.Now.ToString("dd/MM/yyyy");
con3.Open();cmd = new SqlCommand("update FileUpload set
ProxyStatus='Deactivated' where FileName='" + a + "'", con3);
cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();con3.Close();
Response.Write("<script>alert('Deactivated Successfully')</script>");
Response.Redirect("ProxyFileUpload.aspx");
Response.Write("<script>alert('Deactivated Successfully')</script>");}}

```

Transaction

```

<%@Page="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeFile="ProxyTransaction.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ProxyTransaction" %>
<!DOCTYPE html><html lang="zxx"><head><title>Auditing Data</title>
<!-- Meta tag Keywords -->
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta charset="UTF-8" /><meta name="keywords" content="Cakes Bakery
Services Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates,
Android Compatible web template, Smartphone Compatible web template, free
webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design"
/><script>
addEventListener("load", function () {setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);}, false);
function hideURLbar() {window.scrollTo(0, 1);}</script>
<!-- //Meta tag Keywords --><!-- Custom-Files -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.css"><!-- Bootstrap-Core-CSS -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/style.css" type="text/css" media="all" />
<RowStyle BackColor="#FFF7E7" ForeColor="#8C4510" />
<SelectedRowStyleBackColor="#738A9C" Font-Bold="True" ForeColor=White/>

```

```

<script src="js/easing.js"></script>
<!-- necessary snippets for few javascript files -->
<script src="js/cakes-bakery.js"></script><script src="js/bootstrap.js"></script>
<!-- Necessary-JavaScript-File-For-Bootstrap --><!-- //Js files --></body></html>
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
public partial class ProxyTransaction : System.Web.UI.Page{
protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e){}

```

File Download

```

<%@PageLanguage="C#" AutoEventWireup="true"
CodeFile="EndUserDownloadFile.aspx.cs" Inherits="EndUserDownloadFile" %>
<!DOCTYPE html><html lang="zxx"><head><title>Auditing Data</title>
<!-- Meta tag Keywords -->
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta charset="UTF-8" /><meta name="keywords" content="Cakes Bakery
Services Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates,
Android Compatible web template, Smartphone Compatible web template, free
webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design"
/><script>
addEventListener("load", function () {setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);}, false);
function hideURLbar() {window.scrollTo(0, 1);}
</script><!-- //Meta tag Keywords --><!-- Custom-Files -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.css"><!-- Bootstrap-Core-CSS -->

```

```

<!-- menu-js --><script> $('toggle').toggleClass('toggle--active');</script>
<!-- //menu-js --><!-- smooth scrolling -->
<script src="js/SmoothScroll.min.js"></script><!-- move-top -->
<script src="js/move-top.js"></script><!-- easing -->
<script src="js/easing.js"></script>
<!-- necessary snippets for few javascript files -->
<script src="js/cakes-bakery.js"></script><script src="js/bootstrap.js"></script>
<!-- Necessary-JavaScript-File-For-B
cmd4 = new SqlCommand("insert into AuditDetails values('" + TextBox3.Text +
"', 'File Sent To Mail', '" + TextBox2.Text + "', '" + DateTime.Now.ToString() + '"",
con4);cmd4.ExecuteNonQuery();con4.Close();mail();}
else{con4.Open();cmd4 = new SqlCommand("insert into AuditDetails values('" +
TextBox3.Text + "', 'Key Mismatch', '" + TextBox2.Text + "', '" +
DateTime.Now.ToString() + '"", con4;
cmd4.ExecuteNonQuery();con4.Close();
Response.Write("<script>alert('Invalid Key')</script>");}
con2.Close();}
con.Close();}
protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e){
con.Open();
con.Close();
}
protected void Button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
Panel1.Visible = false;
con.Open();

```

```

cmd = new SqlCommand("select * from FileRequest where FileName='" +
TextBox3.Text + "' and FileKey='Waiting' and UserMailID='" + TextBox1.Text +
"'", con);
dr = cmd.ExecuteReader();
if (dr.Read())
{
con4.Open();
cmd4 = new SqlCommand("insert into AuditDetails values('" + TextBox3.Text +
"', 'Key Mismatch', '" + TextBox2.Text + "', '" + DateTime.Now.ToString() + "')",
con4);
cmd4.ExecuteNonQuery();
con4.Close();
Response.Write("<script>alert('Invalid Key')</script>");
}
con4.Close();
string filename = dr1[0].ToString();
string filetype = dr1[3].ToString();
string ext = Path.GetExtension(filetype);

Response.ContentType = dr1["ContentType"].ToString();
Response.AddHeader("Content-Disposition", "attachment;filename=\"\" +
dr1["FileName"] + ext);
Response.BinaryWrite((byte[])dr1["Data"]);
Response.End();}
con1.Close();
}
else

```

```
{
con4.Open();
cmd4 = new SqlCommand("insert into AuditDetails values('" + TextBox3.Text +
"', 'Key Mismatch', '" + TextBox2.Text + "', '" + DateTime.Now.ToString() + '")",
con4);
cmd4.ExecuteNonQuery();
con4.Close();
Response.Write("<script>alert('Invalid Key')</script>");
}
con2.Close();
}
con.close(); }}
```

B.SCREENSHOTS

HOME

PROXY LOGIN

CLIENT REGISTER

CLIENT LOGIN

END USER REGISTER

END USER LOGIN

CLOUD SERVER LOGIN

KGC LOGIN

FILE UPLOAD

FILE SEARCH AND REWRITE

CHECK DATA INTEGRITY

CLIENT INFORMATION

AUTHORIZE FILE UPLOAD

File Information

ClientName	FileName	UploadFile	Date	ProxyStatus	Activate	Deactivate
Vicky	File5	Vicky.txt	01/11/2018	Activated	Click	Click
Vicky	File4	New Text Document.txt	01/11/2018	Activated	Click	Click
Vicky	File3	New Text Document.txt	01/11/2018	Activated	Click	Click
Pavi	File2	Vicky.txt	01/11/2018	Activated	Click	Click
Vicky	File1	Vicky.txt	01/11/2018	Activated	Click	Click
Vicky	File0	New Text Document.txt	01/11/2018	Activated	Click	Click

TRANSACTION

Transaction Information

File Name	Status	User Name	Date
File1	File Download	Priya	11/3/2018 3:38:37 PM
File1	Key Mismatch	Priya	11/3/2018 3:18:42 PM
File1	File Download	Priya	11/3/2018 3:18:38 PM
File1	File Sent To Mail	Priya	11/3/2018 3:18:28 PM
File1	Key Mismatch	Priya	11/3/2018 3:17:56 PM
File1	Key Mismatch	Priya	11/3/2018 3:17:50 PM
File1	Key Mismatch	Priya	11/3/2018 3:16:56 PM
File1	Key Mismatch	Priya	11/3/2018 3:16:51 PM
File1	File Download	Priya	11/3/2018 3:16:43 PM
File1	Key Mismatch	Priya	11/3/2018 2:35:52 PM
File1	Key Mismatch	Priya	11/3/2018 2:35:46 PM

FILE DETAILS

Cloud Server / View Files

File Details				
ID	ClientName	FileName	UploadFile	Date
6	Vicky	File5	Vicky.txt	01/11/2018
5	Vicky	File4	New Text Document.txt	01/11/2018
4	Vicky	File3	New Text Document.txt	01/11/2018
3	Pavi	File2	Vicky.txt	01/11/2018
2	Vicky	File1	Vicky.txt	01/11/2018
1	Vicky	File0	New Text Document.txt	01/11/2018

KEY GENERATE

KGC / Key Generate

Key Generate				
File Name	Upload File	Date	File Key	Generate Key
File5	Vicky.txt	01/11/2018	347698	Click
File4	New Text Document.txt	01/11/2018	547238	Click
File3	New Text Document.txt	01/11/2018	953478	Click
File2	Vicky.txt	01/11/2018	268954	Click
File1	Vicky.txt	01/11/2018	932847	Click
File0	New Text Document.txt	01/11/2018	689305	Click

FILE SEARCH

USER KEY REQUEST

User Key Request

User Name	File Name	Status	Date	Send Key	Block
Priya	File1	Download	11/3/2018 11:10:39 AM	Click	Click
Priya	File3	Blocked	11/2/2018 6:43:44 PM	Click	Click
Priya	File1	Download	11/2/2018 6:32:38 PM	Click	Click

FILE DOWNLOAD

File Download

priya@gmail.com

Priya

File Name

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